

A REMARK ON $A + B$ AND $A - A$ FOR COMPACT SETS IN \mathbb{R}^n

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Abstract

We prove in particular that if $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is a compact convex set, and $B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is an arbitrary compact set, then $\mu(A - A) \ll \frac{\mu(A+B)^2}{\sqrt{n}\mu(A)}$, provided that $\mu(B) \geq \mu(A)$.

1. Introduction

A well-known Ruzsa triangle inequality states that for any finite subsets of an abelian group we have

$$|A - B| \leq \frac{|A + C||C + B|}{|C|};$$

in particular, if $B = A$ and $C = B$, then

$$|A - A| \leq \frac{|A + B|^2}{|B|}.$$

The aim of this note is to prove a sharp, up to a dimension-independent constant, form of the above inequality for a compact convex set $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, and an arbitrary compact set $B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$, provided that $\mu(A) \geq \mu(B)$.

2. Result

For a set $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ and $x \in A - A$ let $A_x = A \cap (A - x)$. Our main tool is the following lemma proved in [4, Lemma 5]. We recall its proof as it is very simple.

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Lemma 1. *Let $A, B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be compact sets. Then*

$$\int_{A-A} \mu(A_x + B) dx \leq \mu(A + B)^2. \tag{1}$$

Proof. We apply the Koester-Katz transform: if $x \in A - A$ then

$$A_x + B \subseteq (A + B)_x.$$

Therefore, we have

$$\int_{A-A} \mu(A_x + B) dx \leq \int_{A+B-A-B} \mu((A + B)_x) dx = \mu(A + B)^2,$$

and the assertion follows. □

We also need a lower bound for the size of A_x for a convex set A , see [5, Section 3]. We also give the proof for the sake of completeness.

Lemma 2. *Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a compact convex set and $r \in [0, 1]$ be any real number. Then for all $x \in r(A - A)$ the following holds:*

$$\mu(A_x) \geq (1 - r)^n \mu(A). \tag{2}$$

Proof. Write $x = ra_1 - ra_2$, where $a_1, a_2 \in A$ and let $a \in A$ be any element. By convexity, $(1 - r)a + ra_1 \in A$ and $(1 - r)a + ra_1 = (1 - r)a + ra_2 + x \in A + x$. Thus $(1 - r)A + ra_1 \subseteq A \cap (A + x)$ and the result follows. □

Finally, we recall the Brunn-Minkowski inequality, see [5, Section 3].

Theorem 1. *Let $A, B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be non-empty compact sets. Then*

$$\mu(A + B)^{1/n} \geq \mu(A)^{1/n} + \mu(B)^{1/n}.$$

Now we can formulate our main result.

Theorem 2. *Let $A \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be a compact convex set, and let $B \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ be an arbitrary compact set. Then*

$$(1 + \omega + \dots + \omega^{\lfloor \sqrt{n} \rfloor}) \mu(B)^{1-1/n} \mu(A)^{1/n} \mu(A - A) \ll \mu(A + B)^2, \tag{3}$$

where $\omega = (\mu(A)/\mu(B))^{1/n}$. In particular, if $\mu(A) \geq \mu(B)$ then

$$\mu(A - A) \ll \frac{\mu(A + B)^2}{\sqrt{n} \mu(A)^{1/n} \mu(B)^{1-1/n}}, \tag{4}$$

and if $\mu(B) \geq \mu(A)$ then

$$\mu(A - A) \ll \frac{\mu(A + B)^2}{\sqrt{n}\mu(A)}. \tag{5}$$

Proof. Let $\alpha = \mu(B)/\mu(A)$. Applying (1) and the Brunn-Minkowski inequality, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^2(A + B) &\geq \int_{A-A} \mu(B + A_x) dx \geq \int_{A-A} \left(\mu(B)^{1/n} + \mu(A_x)^{1/n}\right)^n dx \\ &= \alpha \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \int_{A-A} \alpha^{-k/n} \mu(A)^{(n-k)/n} \mu(A_x)^{k/n} dx. \end{aligned}$$

To estimate the size of A_x we use Lemma 2. After integration by parts, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mu^2(A + B) &\geq \mu(B) \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} k \alpha^{-k/n} \int_0^1 (1-r)^{k-1} \mu(r(A - A)) dr \\ &= \mu(B)\mu(A - A) \sum_{k=1}^n \binom{n}{k} k \alpha^{-k/n} \int_0^1 (1-r)^{k-1} r^n dr \\ &= \mu(B)\mu(A - A) \sum_{k=1}^n \binom{n}{k} k \alpha^{-k/n} \mathcal{B}(k, n + 1), \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathcal{B}(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the beta function. Thus

$$\mu^2(A + B) \geq \mu(B)\mu(A - A) \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha^{-k/n} \frac{(n!)^2}{(n-k)!(n+k)!} := \mu(B)\mu(A - A) \times \sigma.$$

One can calculate the last sum σ using the gamma function or hypergeometric series, but we use a rather crude estimate. Put $\Delta = \lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil + 1$; then

$$\sigma = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha^{-\frac{k}{n}} \prod_{j=1}^{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{j}{n}\right) \prod_{j=1}^k \left(1 + \frac{j}{n}\right)^{-1} = \sum_{k=1}^n \alpha^{-\frac{k}{n}} \left(1 + \frac{k}{n}\right)^{-1} \prod_{j=1}^{k-1} \left(1 - \frac{2j}{n+j}\right).$$

Using inequalities $\ln(1 - x) \geq -2x$ for $0 \leq x \leq 0.5$ and $k \leq n$, we obtain

$$\sigma \geq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\Delta} \alpha^{-k/n} \exp\left(-\sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \frac{4j}{n+j}\right) \geq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\Delta} \alpha^{-k/n} \exp\left(-\frac{2k^2}{n}\right) \gg \sum_{k=1}^{\Delta} \omega^k.$$

This gives us (3). To see (4), it is enough to observe that if $\mu(A) \geq \mu(B)$ then $\sum_{k=1}^{\Delta} \omega^k \geq \sqrt{n}$. To get (5), take any subset B' of B such that $\mu(B') = \mu(A)$ and apply (4); then

$$\mu(A - A) \ll \frac{\mu(A + B')^2}{\sqrt{n}\mu(A)} \leq \frac{\mu(A + B)^2}{\sqrt{n}\mu(A)}.$$

This completes the proof. □

Remark 1. Estimate (4) is tight; see [2] or [3] (discussion after Corollary 8.3). Indeed, consider the n -dimensional simplex

$$A = A_L = \{(x_1, \dots, x_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n : x_j \geq 0, \sum_{j=1}^n x_j \leq L\},$$

where L is a parameter. Then $\mu(A + A) = 2^n \mu(A)$ and $\mu(A - A) = \binom{2n}{n} \mu(A)$ (to obtain the last formula, one can count the number of integer points in A , say, and approximate $\mu(A - A)$ by

$$\sum_{a+b+c=n} \binom{n}{a, b, c} \binom{L}{a} \binom{L}{b} \sim \frac{L^n}{n!} \sum_{m=0}^n \binom{n}{m}^2 = \frac{L^n}{n!} \binom{2n}{n} = \mu(A) \binom{2n}{n};$$

see [1]. Here a, b and c , are the number of possibilities for the positive, negative and zero coordinates in $A - A$, respectively). Hence

$$\mu(A - A) \gg \frac{\mu(A + A)^2}{\sqrt{n} \mu(A)}.$$

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